

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: CAMARA****FIRST NAME: GUIBRIL****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 365

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING AND DIPLOMATIC COMMUNICATION

1) INTRODUCTION

I have always been concerned with the need to communicate properly in the institutions where I have worked. The reason is for that is the potential critical impact of misunderstandings. This situation occurred to me in the military. Within and across diverse, multicultural and multilingual environments like the United Nations, the requirement for the use of adequate communication codes and channels are equally important. Still, there is, built in the system, both a degree of tolerance and a necessity for rigour. Such indulgence is not only linked to the existence of many different types of English, including the British one used here. It partly relates to the fact that many actors are non-native English speakers, while cultural and specialist perspectives easily skew perceptions and messages. Nevertheless, the diplomatic sphere is a more-or-less hardcoded world where actors need to abide by a certain number of shared rules and traditions without being overly rigid. Academic writing is not much different due to its codes that must be respected for the essence to be understood and taken seriously. It is precisely those codes that EUCLID's ACA-401D period one course outlines for the content of one's academic research and reflection to be adequately captured and taken seriously. In yet another analogy, I found the course material to be as overwhelming as the communication codes described in diplomacy (Murty 1989). Nevertheless, I am grateful for the 14-minutes video, which provides a summary of those codes required when writing doctoral-level papers or drafting quizzes. I remain, however, aware that the only way to master the art is by practising.

2) LEARNING THE TOOLS OF THE TRADE

Reading ACA-401D coursepack further convinced me that academic writing, like diplomatic communications, requires one to learn the tools of the trade, literally. It is undoubtedly not about overintellectualizing the form, if not the field of academic writing, as it must remain accessible and stay ultimately relevant and useful for human knowledge and lives. For me, this quest for relevancy correlates well with the rule of thumbs for writing provided in chapter 3 of the coursepack. I will not enumerate them all here, but I am particularly interested in the reminder to “**state the main thesis**”, to “**stay focused**” and specific, “**not [to] make the writing boring and clumsy**”, as well as to “**support assertions**” (EUCLID 2019, 14–15).

Keeping in mind the rationale of doctoral studies which aim at pushing the boundaries of human knowledge and practice in a specific domain, the tools of the trade of academic writing become clearer. Although the objective of pushing the knowledge envelope of humankind may not always be attained when writing doctoral-level papers, or even dissertation, I am convinced that these outputs should at least pave the way for such a goal for readers and other researchers. To be directly or indirectly useful when writing, I know the importance of learning and using the tools of the trade properly. I, therefore, commit myself to learn them continuously during all the DSDD curriculum and beyond, to be able to convey and discuss ideas using the adequate form.

Two aspects that emerge from these tools are similar to the ambivalence of diplomatic communication I referred to in the introduction. With relations to academic writing, I see that ambivalence in the requirement for rigour, while being balanced.

3) AN EXERCISE OF RIGOUR

Essay writing introduced as the first topic in the coursepack is a straightforward part. Very early on, in our academic curriculum, I, like other students, received training on the writing of essays at school. From experience, few, however, ever manage to master it, even at the university level. Personally, despite years of practice, I often find myself caught making common mistakes. These include rushing too fast to the writing part without adequately analysing the question, not precisely tackling what I announced in the introduction, or forcing my first draft to be the final one. That is why the course material is useful. It reminds me of the aim of writing, as well as the steps to follow when drafting a paper. The document states, “an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence”. It further provides a much-useful reminder of the “basic steps [to be used] in writing an essay” (EUCLID 2019, 1).

Turabian style is new to me. The style I was used to is APA. That’s why, I needed to adjust whenever I had to cite, for instance, making sure no comma exists between the author(s) and the year of the publication of the reference in in-text citations (Turabian 2013). Rigour is clearly to be demonstrated at this level. Moreover, the need for exercising rigour is essential when it is about giving credit when credit is due. That is

why I like the second chapter of the course material dealing with plagiarism. The practice is rightly labelled as “wrong and unethical” and “a serious academic offence that can have serious consequences”(EUCLID 2019, 5). The course chapter also continues in explaining how to cite, paraphrase and quote, including using the in-text citations just like the ones in this first response paper. Added to the interdiction to plagiarize, staying focused, writing clearly and supporting assertions are “some [among other] rules of thumb for writing papers” provided in chapter 3 of the course material (EUCLID 2019, 14–16) that I find particularly meaningful and necessitating utmost of my attention.

Finally, I found particularly useful the possibility to leverage tools like Grammarly and Zotero suggested in the Initial Student Orientation document as well as to rely on the templates provided during the first study period of ACA-401D, with pre-formatted fields. These tools reduce the possibility to break prescribed academic codes.

4) A COMPLEX BALANCING ACT

“Effective communication is no more and no less than a complex balancing act, regrettably, with no safety net” (Slavik 2004). In the same way, I also do believe academic writing needs to be balanced both in structure and content. Body parts must be of equal or close sizes and in its content, as reminded in the course material (EUCLID 2019, 2). Still, ACA-401D seems to be providing a pole aimed at preventing falls, rather than mitigating the consequences of eventual falls, as would a safety net do.

Another balance is also rightly highlighted between personal and academic style (EUCLID 2019, 12). The exercise does not seem to be very different from the diplomatic communication referred to earlier. While strict codes exist, I remain aware of the necessity to be authentic and add value. I further believe that the balance between respect of norms and demonstration of authenticity which requires practice can be reached by applying the principles reminded in the course material, and stating that “essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking” (EUCLID 2019, 2). Passage of the small cartoons in the web page of the course one period dealing with the purpose of writing translates well the balancing endeavour to “inflate weak ideas, obscure poor reasoning, and inhibit clarity”.

Finally, on an organisational level, I find advises about time management very useful when writing academic essays, as it allows to avoid procrastination, and spike of intense but often rushed undertakings. It has to do with rigour but also with a proper repartition of tasks. Such repartition will indeed allow to iterate as much as necessary through all the steps of the writing process. The rigour in using proper organisation and repartition of efforts will help reduce stress, and make the writing experience enjoyable, if not less painful.

5) CONCLUSION

A bit of a “Jack of all trade”, I have always wanted to master the art of communicating persuasively. The motivation was not only for professional objectives but also for personal ones, in particular, in challenging intercultural environments. Just like in diplomatic communication, academic requires knowing the tools of the trade. The opportunity to study and research about sustainable development and diplomacy under the DSDD curriculum is one for further learning the tools and practising the art of writing persuasively using the right codes. In this regard, ACA-401D is undoubtedly the right place to start with its rich supporting material, but also helpful shortcuts that allows one to get quickly onboard. I am convinced that practising through the upcoming response and major papers will allow me to “hold the drifts of language and culture” (Slavik 2004, 58). But, before being able to master the art of academic writing or diplomatic communication, I need to know well the underlying sciences. My motivation to learn and the support of the instructors will allow me to achieve the desired outcome.

REFERENCES

- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.
- Murty, Bhagevatula Satyanarayana. 1989. *The International Law of Diplomacy: The Diplomatic Instrument and World Public Order*. Martinus Nijhoff Publishers.
- Slavik, Hannah. 2004. *Intercultural Communication and Diplomacy*. Diplo Foundation.
- Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.